

Voltage Sensitive Cyanine Dye

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2-(4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxystyryl)quinoline ethiodide (a cyanine dye) shows colour sensitivity when DC potential is applied. Under optimised experimental conditions of concentration of dye, pH, time of application, temperature etc, voltage (DC) applied is directly proportional to ΔA , of the dye at its λ_{\max} 475 nm. The probable mechanism of this phenomenon is explained.

Voltage sensitive dyes change absorbance with application of DC potential. This property can be used to measure membrane potentials¹ inside the living cells and to use them for the monitoring of cellular electrical activity². This change of colour intensity of the dye with application of DC potential can also be used as a potentiometric indicator.

A dye 2-(4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-2-ethoxystyryl)quinoline ethiodide (1) was tried as voltage sensitive dye. It was synthesised by the condensation of 2-methoxy-4-*N,N*-bis-2'-cyanoethylamino-benzaldehyde with quinoline ethiodide in ethanol medium. The red coloured liquid on cooling deposited crystals of the dyestuff, which was recrystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

It was found in all the dyes we studied that the difference in absorbance of a dye before and after application of voltage (ΔA) is directly proportional to the voltage applied in a particular range. This relationship between voltage and absorbance will be useful at such places where dipping of electrode may not be convenient or feasible. This is possible when the system itself is colourless or does not interfere in any way with the dye that is added to it.

Decolourisation in the case of this cyanine dye may be due to oxidation process which takes place at anode where I^- oxidises to I_2 , and removal of I^- ions from the solution. This was further confirmed by the addition of $AgNO_3$ solution to the dye solution, the precipitate of AgI forms and supernatant becomes totally colourless. The colourless

liquid was decanted and KI was added when the colour reappeared showing I^- plays a part in the colour of the dye. But the removal of iodide may not be a single factor. Disturbance of conjugation decreases in the length of vibrating chain and loss of chromophore can also cause decolourisation. The formation of leucobase can also give rise to colourless form as it was observed in methylene blue, azene, safranin T and rhodamine when DC potential was applied³. The decolourisation can be due to either one or all reasons mentioned.

Cyanine dye possesses positive charge at their hetero-atoms and conjugated double bonds. These two factors may be responsible for the phenomenon of resonance due to their highly delocalised positive charge and their voltage sensitive property. Similarly the dye which was selected by us also has delocalised positive charge. It might be one of the reasons for its voltage sensitive property. If the conjugation of the vibrating chain responsible for the deep colour of the dyes is disturbed or broken, it is very likely that the colour intensity or colour itself may change even to a colourless molecule with no absorption in the visible region. The change of pH to acidic medium does not change the colour of dye unless DC potential is applied.

Experimental

Absorbance measurement was taken on UV-visible a Beckman 26 spectrophotometer. The absorption maximum was found at 475 nm, and after applying voltage, the colour intensity faded out finally to a colourless solution. DC voltage was applied with the help of a Systronics 613 transistor power supply in the range 0–30 V at a maximum current of 2 A.

Procedure: An aqueous solution ($9.49 \times 10^{-5} M$) of the dye was prepared. Required aliquots of the solution were taken and made upto 100 ml for further use. Pt-Pt electrodes (Elico EP 79) were dipped in the aqueous solutions and DC potential was applied. Various experimental parameters like pH, temperature, concentration of the dye,

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time of applying the voltage, light, stirring and voltage range were studied and optimised to give the highest and/or constant ΔA values for the system.

Mild stirring (50 rpm) had no significant effect on ΔA values and further work was carried out with mild stirring. Same ΔA values were obtained when the experiment was carried out either in dark or in daylight. Temperature in the range 25–40° had no significant effect hence all the experiments were carried out at room temperature. ΔA values increased with increasing concentration of the dye. So concentration $2.37 \times 10^{-5} M$ was chosen for further studies.

It was observed that ΔA altered with change in the pH. ΔA increased with decrease in pH and at very low pH, dye decolorised quickly when DC voltage was applied. pH 1.0 was selected for further work as it gave highest ΔA value and remained stable in the pH range 1.0–2.0. Above 2.0 pH ΔA value decreased. The pH of the solution before and after applying voltage remained the same indicating that decrease in colour intensity is not due to change in pH.

Above optimised conditions were maintained to study of effect of variation of time. ΔA increased with the time of application of voltage and the solution became decolourised within 6 min giving constant ΔA values.

It was observed that there is general linear increase in ΔA with increase in voltage from 1.0 to 3.5 V. This was verified by least-square analysis. Reproducibility of the values was verified by repeating this study six times, which gave relative standard deviation as 2.1 to 0.59% in the voltage range 1.05–3.48 V.

References

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